

The universe formed by Kerr black holes

Author: Junjie Xu

summary

Through a coordinate transformation, we can regard the internal spacetime of a Kerr black hole as a universe. We can utilize a new coordinate system to study the internal spacetime of the Kerr black hole, primarily focusing on the region between the inner event horizon and the outer event horizon. What is the difference between the Kerr black hole universe and the Schwarzschild black hole universe? I am very curious to see what the internal spacetime of a Kerr black hole looks like in the new coordinate system. I didn't expect that just the addition of the rotation condition would make the internal spacetime of a Kerr black hole vastly different from that of a Schwarzschild black hole. This article will discuss how the universe represented by the internal spacetime of a Kerr black hole evolves.

1. Introduction

In my previous article^[1], I regarded the internal spacetime of a Schwarzschild black hole as a universe, established a new coordinate system in its inner region, In this new coordinate system, discussions were held on issues such as how the universe evolves and what dark energy is. However, Schwarzschild black holes are non-rotating, and it is almost impossible for such black holes to exist in the universe. We can continue to study the internal spacetime of a Kerr black hole using the same method. This article mainly focuses on the region between the outer event horizon and the inner event horizon of a Kerr black hole^[2]. In the Boyer-Lindquist coordinate system^[3], under the convention $(-, +, +, +)$, the 11-component of the black hole metric is less than 0 in this region, The 00-component of the metric is greater than 0 in this region, We can establish a coordinate system in which t and r are interchanged in this region and conduct research based on it. The Boyer-Lindquist coordinate system is chosen because it is the coordinate system of an observer in a flat spacetime at a distant point.

The Kerr metric has a cross term, which disappears at infinity. The presence of this cross term indicates that the time basis vector and the azimuthal basis vector of the black hole are not orthogonal, but this also reflects the physical significance of rotating black holes^[4]. In the new coordinate system, the cross term will also change.

Following the same approach as the previous article, the spacetime structure inside a black hole is interpreted as a new cosmological model through a coordinate transformation.

2. The internal spacetime of a Kerr black hole

2.1 Kerr metric

In the Boyer-Lindquist coordinate system, the metric of a Kerr black hole is as follows:

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} -(1 - \frac{2Mr}{\Sigma}) & 0 & 0 & -\frac{2aMr \sin^2 \theta}{\Sigma} \\ 0 & \Sigma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \Delta & 0 \\ -\frac{2aMr \sin^2 \theta}{\Sigma} & 0 & 0 & (r^2 + a^2 + \frac{2a^2Mr \sin^2 \theta}{\Sigma}) \sin^2 \theta \end{pmatrix}$$

Where Σ and Δ are:

$$\Sigma = r^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta$$

$$\Delta = r^2 - 2Mr + a^2$$

M represents the mass of a black hole.

$a = J/M$, where a represents the angular momentum per unit mass.

c is set to the geometric unit system, with $c=1$, and $G=1$.

The radius of the outer event horizon is:

$$r_+ = M + \sqrt{M^2 - a^2}$$

2.2 New coordinate system and metric

Similarly, I need to establish a transformation relationship first, which is as follows:

$$t' = r_+ - r$$

$$r' = ct$$

$$\theta' = \theta$$

$$\varphi' = \varphi$$

The new basis vector is:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial ct'} = \frac{\partial}{\partial ct} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial r}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial r'} = \frac{\partial ct}{\partial r'} \frac{\partial}{\partial ct} = \frac{\partial}{\partial ct}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta'} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi'} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi}$$

Based on the Kerr metric and the new basis vectors, a new metric can be determined.

Based on the previous coordinate transformation, we can know that $r = r_+ - t'$.

Δ is:

$$\Delta = r^2 - 2Mr + a^2 = (r_+ - t')^2 + 2M(r_+ - t') + a^2$$

Σ is:

$$\Sigma = r^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta' = (r_+ - t')^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta'$$

The 00 component of the metric is:

$$g_{00} = \frac{\Sigma}{\Delta} = \frac{(r_+ - t')^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta'}{(r_+ - t')^2 + 2M(r_+ - t') + a^2}$$

The 11 component of the metric is:

$$g_{11} = \frac{2M(r_+ - t')}{(r_+ - t')^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta'} - 1$$

The 22 component of the metric is:

$$g_{22} = (r_+ - t')^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta'$$

The 13 or 31 component of the metric is:

$$g_{13} = -\frac{2a^2 M(r_+ - t') \sin^2 \theta'}{(r_+ - t')^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta'}$$

In the region between the outer event horizon and the inner event horizon, the final moment should be:

$$t' = r_+ - r_- = M + \sqrt{M^2 - a^2} - M + \sqrt{M^2 - a^2} = 2\sqrt{M^2 - a^2}$$

2.3 The 11 components of the metric

For convenience, from here on, the new coordinates will not include the ' symbol.

$$g_{11} = \frac{2M(r_+ - t)}{(r_+ - t)^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta} - 1$$

Let's first take a look at what the spatial radius looks like when $t=0$.

Substitute $t=0$ into g_{11} , we get:

$$g_{11} = \frac{a^2 - a^2 \cos^2 \theta}{2M^2 + 2M\sqrt{M^2 - a^2} - a^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta}$$

When $\theta=\pi/2$, the 11 component is the square of a . When $\theta=0$, the 11 component is 0. This indicates that the initial shape of the universe's space resembles the shape of an inscribed circle pair.

So, when will it expand to its maximum size?

Calculate the critical points for the 11 components:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{2M(r_+ - t)}{(r_+ - t)^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta} = 0$$

$$t = r_+ \pm a \cos \theta$$

Substitute the critical point into the 11 component equation to obtain the extreme value:

$$t = r_+ - a \cos \theta$$

$$g_{11} = \frac{2Ma \cos \theta}{(a \cos \theta)^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta} - 1 = \frac{M}{a \cos \theta} - 1$$

When the universe expands to its maximum, its radius becomes infinitely large at θ equals $\pi/2$, while it remains finite at other angles, resembling the shape of a lip-kissing circle.

$$t = r_+ + a \cos \theta$$

$$g_{11} = -\frac{M}{a \cos \theta} - 1$$

To ensure that the 11th component is positive, we need to discard the second one. Since we have defined a range, we are now discussing the region between the inner and outer event horizons. t cannot exceed the final time, and $r_+ + a \cos \theta$ is already greater than r_+ .

As time passes, the radius of space will continue to expand until it reaches a certain extent. What will happen after that?

Let's substitute the last moment into the 11 component and have a look:

$$t = 2\sqrt{M^2 - a^2}$$

$$g_{11} = \frac{2M(r_+ - t)}{(r_+ - t)^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta} - 1$$

$$= \frac{2Mr_-}{r_-^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta} - 1$$

$$= \frac{2M^2 - 2M\sqrt{M^2 - a^2}}{M^2 - 2M\sqrt{M^2 - a^2} + M^2 - a^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta} - 1$$

$$= \frac{a^2 - a^2 \cos^2 \theta}{2M^2 - 2M\sqrt{M^2 - a^2} - a^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta}$$

This is exactly the same as at $t=0$, indicating that the spatial radius will start to contract after expanding to a certain extent, until it shrinks back to the initial state.

2.4 The 22 components of the metric

$$g_{22} = (r_+ - t)^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta$$

When $t=0$:

$$g_{22} = r_+^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta$$

Critical point and extreme value:

$$t = r_+$$

$$g_{22} = a^2 \cos^2 \theta$$

Substitute the last moment into the 22 component, and we get:

$$t = 2\sqrt{M^2 - a^2}$$

$$g_{22} = r_-^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta$$

To summarize, the space contracts in the θ direction first, and then expands in the θ direction.

2.5 The 00 components of the metric

$$g_{00} = \frac{\Sigma}{\Delta} = \frac{(r_+ - t)^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta}{(r_+ - t)^2 + 2M(r_+ - t) + a^2}$$

When $t=0$:

$$g_{00} = \frac{r_+^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta}{r_+^2 + 2Mr_+ + a^2}$$

Substitute the final time into the 00 component, and we obtain:

$$t = 2\sqrt{M^2 - a^2}$$

$$g_{00} = \frac{r_-^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta}{r_-^2 + 2Mr_- + a^2}$$

Regarding the speed of time passing, it should also be easy to guess that at the beginning, time passes quickly, gradually slows down, and then starts to speed up again.

2.6 The 13 or 31 component of the metric

$$g_{13} = -\frac{2a^2 M(r_+ - t) \sin^2 \theta}{(r_+ - t)^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta}$$

When $t=0$:

$$g_{13} = -\frac{2a^2 Mr_+ \sin^2 \theta}{r_+^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta}$$

When $\theta=0$, the 13 component is 0. When $\theta=\pi/2$, the 13 component is finite. Initially, the cross terms appear relatively normal.

Critical point and extreme value:

$$t = r_+ \pm a \cos \theta$$

$$g_{13} = -aM \sin \theta \tan \theta$$

When $\theta=0$, the 13 component is 0. When $\theta=\pi/2$, the 13 component diverges, but this is only due to the choice of coordinate system and is not a true physical singularity. It merely indicates that the radius basis vector and the θ basis vector in the universe space are no longer linearly independent, which is because the radius is infinite when θ equals $\pi/2$.

Substitute the last moment into the 13 component, and we obtain:

$$g_{00} = \frac{r_+^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta}{r_+^2 + 2Mr_+ + a^2}$$

$$g_{13} = -\frac{2a^2 Mr_- \sin^2 \theta}{r_-^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta}$$

When $\theta=0$, the 13 component is 0. When $\theta=\pi/2$, the 13 component is finite. Very close to the initial state.

The cross-term implies that the radius of the universe's space is not orthogonal to θ . Overall, The cross-term becomes increasingly evident at first, and then gradually weakens.

2.7 energy-momentum

In my previous article, I calculated the energy-momentum in the new coordinate system, and the result was 0. This is not surprising, as the Schwarzschild metric is a vacuum solution of Einstein's field equations. Similarly, the Kerr metric is also a vacuum solution of Einstein's field equations, so its energy-momentum in my new coordinate system is also 0. There is no need to calculate it, but this does not mean that black holes have no mass.

3. References

- [1] Junjie, X. (2026). *An enlightening perspective on black holes and the universe*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18261496>.
- [2] Frolov, V. P., & Novikov, I. D. (1998). *Black Hole Physics: Basic Concepts and New Developments*. Springer.
- [3] Boyer, R. H., & Lindquist, R. W. (1967). Maximal Analytic Extension of the Kerr Metric. *Journal of Mathematical Physics*, 8(2), 265–281.
- [4] Kerr, R. P. (1963). Gravitational Field of a Spinning Mass as an Example of Algebraically Special Metrics. *Physical Review Letters*, 11(5), 237–238.